

STUDY OF PARAMETERS OF NON-SPECIFIC RESISTANCE FACTORS OF THE BODY OF WORKERS IN SPINNING PRODUCTION

F.N. Nuraliyev

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15459304>

Abstract. *The textile industry is one of the main industries for the economy of any country in the world. Workers in the textile industry are exposed to a number of chemicals, including dyes, solvents, optical brighteners, finishing agents, and numerous types of natural and synthetic fiber dust. The established increased background of IgA and IgM in workers in the spinning industry indicates the presence of a weak antigenic stimulus, and a decrease in IgE indicates the absence of an allergic background. The activity of humoral immunity is constantly affected by an antigenic stimulus, which leads to tension in the immune system and a pre-pathological state of the body.*

Keywords: *non-specific resistance factors, humoral immunity, immune characteristics of workers, spinning production.*

Introduction. The textile industry is successfully developing in Uzbekistan. The constantly growing demand for textile products both in the domestic and foreign markets and the high labor intensity of production make it possible to provide employment for a large number of people, primarily women in rural areas, and testifies to the social orientation of the industry [4]. The processing of textiles generates a variety of wastes, including liquid, gaseous and solid wastes, some of which pose a hazard to the workers in this production [2].

The body's resistance is the body's resistance to the action of physical, chemical and biological agents that cause a pathological condition, reflects the potential adaptive capabilities of the body, the ability to resist the action of pathogenic agents in specific conditions of existence, characterizes the body's resistance (stability, insensitivity) to the effects of various factors, and to a certain extent characterizes the state of the human immune system [5].

The immune system distinguishes between specific and non-specific resistance factors, which are divided according to their reaction to external stimuli (antigens). Specific protective factors are antigen-dependent, while non-specific resistance factors are independent of antigen exposure [6]. Together they perform the same function – protecting the body from external and internal influences. Antigens can be various substances that meet the inhibiting characteristics; they must be foreign, immunogenic, antigenic and have a sufficient molecular weight [3].

The aim of the study. Evaluation of humoral factors of resistance of the body of workers in the spinning industry.

Materials and research methods. The object of the study was 137 workers of the production cluster of Ark Eko Tekstil LLC, located in Bukhara. The study of immunological parameters was studied by examining the blood serum of workers, which was isolated from their peripheral blood. Before use, the blood serum in the amount of 2-3 ml was stored in a freezer at a subzero temperature. The studies were conducted using the ELISA method with the use of test systems from the Vector-Best company (Novosibirsk, Russian Federation).

Results. Humoral factors of immunity are the “first echelon” of the body’s defense, providing primary and secondary immune responses. The main representatives of humoral immunity are immunoglobulins of various classes, components of the complement system and lactoferrin. In this regard, we considered it appropriate to study and evaluate the quantitative content of the main classes of immunoglobulins - immunoglobulins A, M, G, E (IgA, IgM, IgG, IgE), C3 complement component and lactoferrin in the blood serum of workers in the spinning industry in comparison with these data of healthy individuals [1].

The results obtained for determining different classes of immunoglobulins in the blood serum of the subjects are presented in Table 1.

It is known that IgA is the first line of defense of the body against pathogens, their waste products, etc. It provides local immunity. In our studies, IgA parameters in workers (general group) were 1.53 times higher than in healthy individuals ($P<0.05$).

Table 1

Immunoglobulin content in the blood of workers in spinning production, n=60

Immunoglobulins	In healthy people	For workers
IgA, g/l	1,34±0,05	2,05±0,05*↑
IgM, g/l	1,15±0,06	3,08±0,06*↑
IgG, g/l	9,16±0,33	9,07±0,16
IgE, ME/ml	14,46±1,05	6,92±0,33*↓

Note: * - a sign of reliable difference from healthy individuals, ↑, ↓ - direction of changes.

IgM provides the primary immune response and is the first of the immunoglobulins to react to the entry of an antigen into the body. A large amount of this immunoglobulin in the blood serum is observed in the first 5 days after the entry of the antigen. In our studies, the amount of IgM in workers was 3.08 ± 0.06 g/l, which is 2.68 times higher than in healthy individuals ($P<0.001$).

IgG makes up 75% of all immunoglobulins in the human body, is synthesized after IgM and reaches its highest level on the 28th day after the antigen hits. However, in our studies, the IgG content was virtually identical between healthy individuals and workers.

It has been established that IgE is a precursor to allergic conditions; when an allergic condition is detected, the amount of IgE in the blood serum increases several times. In our studies, the IgE content was at the level of normal values. This indicates that the subjects examined have virtually no allergic background. This means that the industrial hazards of spinning production do not lead to allergic conditions.

Next, we study the content of immunoglobulins in the blood serum of workers in the control and main groups. The results of the research are presented in Table 2.

As can be seen from Table 2, reliable changes were observed in the IgA content in the blood serum of workers in all surveyed workshops – control (sewing workshop, weaving workshop) and main (processing workshop, scutching, carding, spinning workshop) groups ($P<0.001$). The increases were 1.66 and 1.48 times in the control groups and from 1.41 times to 1.63 times in the main groups ($P<0.001$). In addition, changes of the same intensity, only in the direction of decrease, were observed when studying IgE ($P<0.001$). All parameters of the control and main groups were significantly lower by 1.81-2.20 times and 1.94-2.38 times ($P<0.001$), but it should be noted that all parameters were at the level of reference values (from 0 to 10 IU/ml).

Table 2.

The content of immunoglobulins in the blood serum of workers in the control and main groups of spinning production.

Production workshops	IgA, g/l	IgM, g/l	IgG, g/l	IgE, ME/ml
Healthy faces	1,34±0,05	1,15±0,06	9,16±0,33	14,46±1,05
Sewing workshop	2,22±0,08*↑	2,82±0,23*↑	9,15±0,74	7,99±0,75*↓
Weaving workshop	1,98±0,07*↑	2,95±0,17*↑	9,33±0,24	6,57±0,33*↓
Processing workshop	2,05±0,21*↑	3,08±0,20*↑	9,77±0,28	7,45±1,22*↓
Scutching workshop	1,97±0,04*↑	3,19±0,26*↑	8,84±0,36	6,08±0,93*↓
Carding workshop	1,89±0,12*↑	3,23±0,05*↑	8,60±0,22	6,21±0,72*↓
Spinning workshop	2,19±0,05*↑	3,22±0,07*↑	8,71±0,23	7,21±0,69*↓

Note: * - a sign of reliable difference from healthy individuals, ↑, ↓ - direction of changes.

Reliable differences between these workers and healthy individuals were also noted in the content of IgM in the blood serum ($P < 0.001$), where all parameters of the studied contingent were elevated in relation to the data of healthy individuals (1.15 ± 0.06 g/l). In the examined control groups, the indicators were 2.45 times (up to 2.82 ± 0.23 g/l) and 2.57 times (2.95 ± 0.17 g/l) higher than the average value of healthy people ($P < 0.001$). The same trend of changes was found among workers in the main groups – 2.68 times more among workers in the processing shop (3.08 ± 0.20 g/l), 2.77 times more among workers in the scutching shop (3.19 ± 0.26 g/l), 2.81 times more among workers in the carding shop (3.23 ± 0.05 g/l) and 2.80 times more among workers in the spinning shop (3.22 ± 0.07 g/l) – $P < 0.001$. It should be noted that no significant differences were found in the IgG content between the compared groups and the data of healthy individuals ($P > 0.05$); all parameters were at the level of parameters of healthy individuals.

In addition, attention is drawn to the fact that all indicators of workers in the studied and compared workshops of the control and main groups were practically at the same level and did not differ significantly from each other ($P > 0.05$).

Thus, the study of the main immunoglobulins (IgA, IgM, IgG, IgE) in the blood serum of workers in the spinning industry showed an imbalance between the parameters of these immunoglobulins. If IgA and IgM were significantly elevated in relation to healthy individuals ($P < 0.001$), then IgE was significantly reduced in all study groups (control and main groups). The increase in IgA was 1.48-1.66 times, IgM 2.48-2.81 times, IgE decreased 1.81-2.38 times in relation to healthy ($P < 0.001$), there were no reliable differences in the IgG content ($P > 0.05$). It is noteworthy that no reliable differences were found between the indicators of the control (sewing and weaving shops) and main (processing shop, scutching, carding, spinning shops) groups. If we take into account that all parameters of IgA (reference values 1.69-3.85 g/l), IgM (0.89-4.08 g/l), IgG (8.85-13.34 g/l) and IgE (0-100 IU/ml) were at the level or at the upper limit of normal values, then it becomes clear that the parameters of the workers were at the level of normal values. The presence of an elevated background of IgA and IgM indicates the presence of a weak antigen stimulus, and a decrease in IgE indicates the absence of an allergic background. It has been established that the activity of humoral immunity (including local immunity) is constantly distinguished by an antigen stimulus, which leads to tension in the immune system. This fact may be a harbinger of a pre-pathological condition of the body of workers in this production.

In addition, non-specific factors of the body's defense were determined in the blood serum of the examined workers - C3 component of complement (C3C) and lactoferrin (LF). The results of the studies are presented in Table 3.

Table 3.

Comparative indices of complement component C3 and lactoferrin in workers of spinning production

Production workshops	component C3, g/l	Lactoferrin, mkg/ml
Healthy faces	1,28±0,05	247,02±1,13
Sewing workshop	0,50±0,05*↓	361,60±3,63*↑
Weaving workshop	0,69±0,05*↓	353,20±4,84*↑
Processing workshop	0,64±0,05*↓	354,60±6,23*↑
Scutching workshop	0,57±0,05*↓	355,10±5,84*↑
Carding workshop	0,71±0,06*↓	355,50±6,05*↑
Spinning workshop	0,73±0,07*↓	362,60±5,51*↑

Note: * - a sign of reliable difference from healthy individuals, ↑, ↓ - direction of changes.

The obtained results show that in workers in the spinning industry, the C3C and LF changed in different directions, if the C3C parameters were significantly reduced in relation to the data of healthy individuals by 1.86-2.56 times in the control groups ($P < 0.001$) and 1.75-2.25 times in the main groups ($P < 0.001$) of the study. But it should be emphasized that all parameters of the examined subjects were within normal values or constituted the lower limit of reference values (0.76-1.8 g/l) - $P > 0.05$. The lactoferrin content was increased in all study groups compared to the data of healthy people ($P < 0.01$), but as in the case of C3C, the data were within the reference values (190-500 ng/ml).

Conclusion. Thus, the study of the content of non-specific protection factors C3C and LF in workers in the spinning industry showed that their quantitative content changed in different directions in relation to healthy individuals, C3C in all groups was significantly reduced ($P < 0.001$), and LF was significantly increased compared to the data of healthy individuals ($P < 0.001$). But given that all parameters of the control and main groups were within the reference values, we believe that non-specific factors of the body's resistance were not involved in the pre-pathological conditions of the body. They are not specific and not sensitive to the influence of production factors, and also do not have diagnostic and prognostic value in determining pre-pathological and pathological conditions of the body of workers in the spinning industry.

REFERENCES

1. Ashish M., Saud A., Arshad R., Moshahid R., Ashish K.M. Expression of epithelial membrane antigen and cytokeratin among Indian workers exposed to cotton fibre dust in textile industries // Eastern Mediterranean health journal. – 2022. – N. 28(2). – P. 152-157.
2. Bhatia S.C., Devraj S. Pollution control in textile industry // WPI publishing. – 2017. – P. 5-16.
3. Istomin A.V., Vasilenko O.A., Sinoda V.A., Ovcharova K.V., Makhotina O.G., Dracheva E.E. Puti povisheniya obshey rezistentnosti organizma pri vozdeystvii neblagopriyatnix faktorov proizvodstvennoy sredi // Zdorove naseleniya i sreda obitaniya. – 2009. – №. 10. – P. 35-37.

4. Slavinskaya N.V., Nuraliyev F.N. Usloviya truda pryadilnogo proizvodstva Buxarskogo tekstilnogo klastera “Ark Eko Tekstil” // Jurnal Gumanitarnix i yestestvennix nauk. – 2023. – №6(12). – P. 158-163.
5. Xaitov R.M. Immunologiya: struktura i funktsii immunnoy sistemi // Obshestvo s ogranichennoy otvetstvennostyu Izdatelskaya gruppya “GEOTAR-Media”. – 2013. – P. 25-30.
6. Zaxarenkov V.V., Kazitskaya A.S., Mixaylova N.N., Romanenko D.V., Jdanova N.N., Jukova A.G. Vliyaniye vrednix proizvodstvennix faktorov na immunnyy status organizma // Meditsina truda i promishlennaya ekologiya. – 2017. – № 12. – C. 19-23.
7. Slavinskaya N.V., Nuraliyev F.N. Osobennosti oxrani zdorovya i viyavlyayemost professionalnoy patologii u rabotnikov // Meditsinskiy jurnal Uzbekistana. - 2023. - №1. - P. 11-19.